

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON DIPLOMACY: HISTORICAL TRADITIONS AND MODERN APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

The article examines and analyzes the impact of globalization on diplomacy: to impact diplomats, diplomatic methods and diplomatic institutions, and the resulting issues. In general, changes in the role and essence of diplomacy at a time of deepening globalization, the application of new approaches in diplomacy, the points that necessitate a new structural change have been highlighted in scientific work. Given that globalization is a process, it can be concluded that its study is still relevant. Although its research has been conducted in many forms, it seems that there is still a need for in-depth and comprehensive research on diplomacy.

Keywords: globalization, diplomacy, diplomatic methods, diplomatic institutions.

1. Introduction

The use of the tool of diplomacy in international relations, which helps to implement the foreign policy of states, is as old as human history, but has been of interest for centuries. Until the time we live, diplomatic activity and the institution of diplomacy are becoming increasingly important. In our rapidly globalizing world, with the rapid intensification of international relations, it is safe to say that diplomatic activity will continue to grow.

As a result of "new problems" and "new actors" in the field of diplomacy, traditional diplomacy has necessitated structural changes in organizations. As a result of rapid changes in the field of communications and transport, heads of state and government, ministers gradually began to assume diplomatic posts. As a result of these developments, it is claimed that the traditional "diplomat" type should be replaced by expert bureaucrats, technicians and politicians [8, p.12].

New and rapidly spreading technology has also changed the political and social context of the old world of diplomacy. The diplomacy of the 21st century, which we can call global diplomacy, is not only a method of diplomacy between states or governments, but also a kind of "civil society diplomacy", unlike the old method[1]. In other words, "new diplomacy" has become a method of diplomacy in which the weight of the public is felt through community-oriented practices.

The solution of "new problems" in the new sphere of communication with global diplomacy and the existence of new actors make it necessary to carry out structural changes in traditional diplomatic organizations. Given the current situation, the diplomacy carried out by the state's foreign relations agencies for peaceful purposes has gone through many stages before reaching this stage.

2. The impact of globalization on diplomats

A diplomat appointed as "a person engaged in foreign policy and appointed to represent his country" was seen as the first method of diplomacy in the history of diplomacy. During this period, diplomatic representatives were temporarily sent abroad to

perform certain duties, and after performing these duties, they were recalled to their home countries.

Important innovations in the history of diplomacy were observed for the first time with the recognition of the right to diplomatic immunity by the Greeks and the emergence of the "proxenos", the first examples of today's consular post. In the ancient Greek city-states, diplomats did not go beyond being ambassadors. Their main task was to carry the message between the city-states. Therefore, the most important feature sought after by these first diplomats was that they had a strong voice and a strong memory that would allow them to remember the message they were conveying [8, p. 16].

Another feature of Greek diplomacy was its openness and democracy. The policy regarding the ambassador's missions was widely discussed in public, and the arguments that the ambassador would use on the other side were clearly defined. The instructions given to the apostles were extremely limited. Although the Greeks were limited, they created a diplomatic archive and a diplomatic language. The Greeks had three types of representatives, called presbys, keyrx, and prexenos. The first two, which could be translated as "messenger" and "old man," respectively, were assigned for short and multi-purpose missions.

Byzantine emperors, for the first time in history, created a public union whose specialty was foreign relations. This section provided training for ambassadors to foreign countries as professional speakers. During this training, ambassadors were taught the protocol and interview method they should pay attention to while performing their duties. In addition, the written instructions given to the ambassadors prior to their appointment reiterated the general and specific issues to be considered.

It was an old tradition to send emissaries to maintain relations between monarchs and rulers. With the steady transition of northern Italian city-states to diplomacy, the experience of the embassy became even more important. Renaissance Italy was important for the development of the diplomatic profession, which has always been active in foreign policy. Although

embassies of professional diplomats were established for the sole purpose of prestige, today they carry out many of the functions of embassies. As diplomats became an important source of information for both allies and enemies, great importance was attached to the diplomats' reports in terms of building the right foreign policy [2, p. 336].

In the 15th and 16th centuries, ambassadors were appointed to foreign countries for two years. They could not take their wives with them on the grounds of gossip, but they had to take their wives with them because of the possibility of poisoning by foreign chefs [13, p. 28]. The main qualities sought in these first permanent diplomats were: *they knew many languages, especially Latin, they were patient, tolerant, calm and hospitable, they were able to control their emotions and were not subject to scandals in their personal lives* [8, p. 19]. In addition, during this period, acts of diplomacy, such as meddling in the internal affairs of the host countries, engaging in destructive activities, espionage, and lying, were considered normal or even legitimate [6, p. 342-343].

Although the Italians formed the concept of diplomacy in the 15th and 16th centuries, the weight of the French in diplomacy was felt in the 18th and 19th centuries. The diplomatic profession began to take shape from professionals. In this century, diplomacy has become a profession, and diplomatic personnel have become a privileged class apart from society. In particular, diplomacy has become a professional group with personal and professional immunity, tax-free, free of customs, a luxurious lifestyle, and respected by the authorities.

Although Harold Nicholsan emphasized the importance of changing the qualities of an ideal diplomat over time and space, he argued that some qualities of a diplomat should not change over time and space. The qualities that an ideal diplomat should have: *accuracy, confidence, calmness, good character, patience, humility and loyalty*. According to a more functional understanding of these qualities, Learche and Said say, *"A diplomat must understand the environment and the field in which he works, be well-defined, be flexible, and be willing to compromise with small concessions."* [6].

In the absence of communications, telegraphs and telephones, as well as vehicles, diplomats were endowed with some decision-making power. In a world where the media is not yet widespread, states have used intelligence from diplomatic missions in those countries as the only source to find out what other countries are up to.

Thus, as the nature of the international system and international relations has changed over time, there have been significant changes in the qualifications required for diplomats. In the Middle Ages and the beginning of the new century, when diplomats were considered personal representatives of rulers, qualities such as the physical structure of diplomats, the beauty of their spouses, and the fact that they were rich and noble were important [3, p. 134]. In the age of communication with globalization, dizzying events have led to many transformations and changes in terms

of the responsibilities of diplomats. For example, at a time when international communications and transportation were accelerated by telegraph, radio, and aviation, the foreign ministries were able to tighten control over foreign diplomats. With the invention of modern means of communication, the independence of diplomatic representatives working in foreign countries and the establishment of foreign policy were more strictly controlled than before [8, p. 62].

Although diplomatic missions were an important decision-making mechanism in foreign policy in the pre-World War I period, the so-called old diploma made the current diplomat an *"official at the end of the line"*. Diplomats who had previously had limited and delayed contact with the headquarters had considerable freedom in the line of duty, where they could only obtain information on the general framework of the subject and make their comments within that general framework. However, the unrestricted development of communication technology began to be replaced by both a common framework and video telephone calls, which severely limited the diplomatic freedoms of diplomats.

Technological developments in the era of globalization, on the one hand, stimulated the diplomatic missions to work more efficiently than in previous periods, on the other hand, created new options for the classical methods of providing information and made them relatively important. In fact, while in what we call "old diplomacy," diplomats attach great importance to intelligence, in a country with a technological revolution brought about by globalization, diplomats learn this information instantly online. In addition, researching local newspapers on a daily basis is one of the main responsibilities of current ambassadors. Diplomats evaluate and comment on newspaper reports in the context of the political, social and economic environment in their countries [8, p. 69].

According to another view, globalization is accompanied by a revolution in technology and communication, which makes society more transparent. In this case, it is emphasized that diplomats should gradually improve their communication skills [14].

Another innovation brought by globalization is personal diplomacy. As it is known, the reception of a country's ambassador is a very important event in the old diplomacy, but in the new diplomacy it seems that such ceremonies are no longer needed. Heads of state and government establish direct contacts with their counterparts through visits, means of communication and telephone conversations, contribute to the promotion of countries, the development of bilateral official and other relations [7, p. 57].

At the end of the visit, he is a diplomat who made vague promises and agreements a reality. The following words of the Canadian ambassador perfectly express today's diplomacy: *"You have been working silently and patiently on something for months, and when everything is ready, a minister comes and signs a paper with a golden pen. After that, everyone in the country says how educated he is and that we diplomats don't need him anymore."* [7, p. 69].

On the other hand, especially since the beginning of the twentieth century, it has begun to develop rapidly in the field of transport, giving different qualities to the concepts of time and space in international politics. Significant shortening of distances between the capitals of countries has allowed not only diplomats, but also foreign ministers or heads of state, who are the direct decision-making bodies of the countries, to participate in meetings to address important issues.

In addition, such events have significantly increased the public's interest and knowledge of foreign policy and, in a sense, revealed the phenomenon of "foreign policy integration." It is a fact that this situation limits the mobility of diplomacy and narrows the possibilities of resolving the problem through diplomacy. Diplomats comment on the information they receive in the country where they live, adding their views to the country's governments and parliaments[15].

In their mission to promote international trade, diplomats both respond to requests from various companies and explore new trade opportunities. This type of task is very new and unusual for traditional diplomats. Diplomats help and guide business people in the field of commerce and educate them about the commercial environment in their country. In addition, the organization of industrial fairs has become one of the important functions of diplomats [7, p. 71].

According to other diplomats, "the ambassador is an honest man sent abroad to lie in favor of his country." Although it is quite normal for diplomats to lie in the old diplomacy, this idea has lost its effect today. In diplomacy, the "moral" debate comes to the fore. According to former US Secretary of State Dean Acheson, "The important goal of diplomacy is to contribute to the good development of sustainable relations between states, and these relations should be conducted in a way that builds mutual trust." To achieve this, diplomacy must follow the same moral and ethical principles that build trust between people. "Today, the main rule is that diplomats refrain from making statements that do not reflect the facts [9].

In recent years, major powers have been particularly prone to the decline of diplomatic missions around the world. The reason for this may be a sharp reduction in costs. Therefore, ambassadors make great efforts to protect and maintain their missions [10].

All these developments have led to a relative reduction in the main functions of diplomacy in the classical sense. On the one hand, diplomatic representatives have lost their unrivaled position in providing political information to the country, on the other hand, the direct participation of diplomats in decision-making processes related to the country's foreign policy has decreased compared to the past.

3. The impact of globalization on diplomatic methods

Perhaps the most important change in the impact of globalization on diplomacy is seen in diplomatic methods. In the twentieth century, the great totalitarian states have developed some new methods of diplomacy. Perhaps the most important feature of the method of diplomacy used until the early twentieth

century is the secrecy of diplomacy. This confidentiality includes not only diplomatic negotiations, but also the results of negotiations. During this period, the country's leaders made even the most important foreign policy decisions in the direction of their personal interests and goals, without consulting the people, even without their knowledge.

At the end of the First World War, the world now faced a different international structure. With the development of technology, the qualities of the concepts of "diplomacy" and "war" have changed. The prevailing principles in interstate relations have changed their nature, and the practice of "secret diplomacy" has given way to the notion of "open diplomacy."

At the end of World War I, US President **Woodrow Wilson** introduced a new concept to diplomacy. The first of the "14 points" announced by President Wilson on January 8, 1918 was: "Open agreements to be reached as a result of open negotiations. After that, diplomacy had to be conducted in public. Open diplomacy has been linked to the realization of modern democracy". According to **Harold Nicholson**, a well-known writer of diplomacy, "new" diplomacy was nothing more than the application of the ideas that are the basis of liberal democracy in domestic politics, as well as in foreign relations [13, p. 73]. The first diplomatic method used in history was "ad hoc". Ad hoc was a one-sided and temporary method of diplomacy. In other words, diplomatic representatives were temporarily sent abroad to perform a specific task, and after completing this task, they returned to their home countries. One of the first examples of the practice of diplomacy is the diplomacy of the ancient Greek city-state [11, p. 22].

Along with the diplomacy of antiquity, with the fifteenth century there was a transition to "sustainable diplomacy", which meant the existence of permanent diplomatic committees before the Italian city-states. The protection of northern Italy by the Alps in the region, the difficulty of other countries' environmental degradation due to limited transport, communications, the Hundred Years' War in Europe and Europe's inability to fight Italy and Europe, the balance of power between these city-states was one of the reasons for its appearance [5, p. 79].

In the 16th century, there was an advanced diplomatic system among the great powers of Europe, formed by the adoption of permanent diplomacy. Diplomacy in these countries has made great strides at the institutional level.

According to experts, after the Vienna Convention, a new diplomatic method began to be used. Today, the relations between the states are more complex, tense and diverse than in the past, which necessitated the multilateralism of bilateral diplomacy. While diplomacy continued between bilateral rules until the seventeenth century, it became a multilateral communication within international organizations, especially in the diplomatic and technical spheres, which developed in the 19th century.

Although multilateral diplomacy, also known as parliamentary diplomacy or conference diplomacy, has

its origins in the Congress of Westphalia, it has developed significantly since the First World War due to the increase in the number of countries, mainly within the United Nations system. The gradual spread of continental and regional cooperation structures has increased the importance of multilateral diplomacy. However, today a new type of diplomacy is being developed in the economic and social aspects of cross-border relations between countries through "Non-Governmental Organizations". Among the most famous, such organizations as Grenpeace, the International Committee of the Red Cross, Amnesty International carry out many activities such as economic development, benefiting international public opinion.

Another new form of governance can be called "good governance" diplomacy. This type of diplomacy is defined as the intervention or assistance of the international community, especially governments, to countries that are unable to pursue policies that are adequate to their societies or that cannot be governed by internal turmoil. Habitat, Rio Summit, etc. conferences, global environmental conferences, security operations of the United Nations and other international powers, the establishment of special commissions within the UN are examples of good governance diplomacy [4, p. 352].

4. The impact of globalization on diplomatic institutions

The end of the Cold War necessitated the collapse of communism, the division of some states into new states, and the emergence of new states that were not under the control of the superpowers. The Institute of Diplomacy also had to keep up with these changes [7, p. 66].

In addition to the foreign ministries and diplomatic staff, many other agencies also play a role in international relations. For example, the Ministries of Labor, Justice, Home Affairs, Treasury, and Agriculture may establish direct contacts with other government officials in their respective fields and establish contacts with international organizations. In the context of the development of these relations, it should be noted that the relations carried out through the foreign ministries and embassies in Western countries have replaced them.

As globalization seems to be a natural phenomenon, the state system is gradually becoming part of global politics. In this system, diplomats are expected to participate in some form of different policies, negotiations will expand, and mediation will be the key to diplomatic methods. Diplomats are expected to play a mediating role between the state and politics in this system [12].

Although traditional embassies in the capitals, which are the traditional form of diplomatic missions, still retain their importance, their functions have changed. The number of special missions sent by foreign ministries in mediation missions has increased. The development of summit diplomacy through meetings in international organizations is more crucial in diplomacy. In fact, multilateral relations have been

the main framework of diplomacy, without which it is almost impossible to maintain bilateral relations.

5. Conclusion

The study leads to the conclusion that the change in communication and contact brought by globalization has led to the emergence of a method of public diplomacy, and classical diplomacy has been replaced by new changes and perspectives.

This study compares and connects the experiences and processes of individuals, communities and states in the history of mankind in a globalized world, and assesses the contributions and differences of diplomacy in the history of mankind. Although all diplomatic processes differ from each other, it has been shown that they are complementary disciplines. Naturally, the historical process influenced the formation of the digital diplomacy system. The study assessed the sub-dimensions, differences and similarities of diplomacy. After reviewing the results of the study, recommendations for future research and researchers were made within the scope of the study.

It is important for diplomacy to develop, plan, implement and monitor effective strategies to achieve the organization's goals. The organization of digital governance is a very important task of top management, as it is concerned and guides the future of societies. Now international relations revolve around digitalization. While digitalization, which is an important factor on the world agenda, cannot eliminate all old diplomacy and its traditions, it is leading to radical changes in diplomacy.

In today's diplomacy, the main task of a diplomat is to be impartial and honest, to refrain from statements that do not reflect the facts.

In the past, diplomats were very good orators and nobles, but in today's diplomacy, it is a common requirement for a diplomat to have a very good education and professional experience, to study law and economics.

References

1. Aras B. Küresel dönüşüm radikal yaklaşımlar / İstanbul: Q-Matris yayınları, - 2004, - 220 s.
2. Arı T. Uluslararası ilişkiler teorileri: çatışma, hegemonya, işbirliği / İstanbul: Alfa yayınevi, - 2002, - 582 s.
3. Gönülbol M. Uluslararası politika. İlkeler, kavramlar kurumlar / Ankara: Atilla kitabevi, - 1993, - 588 s.
4. İskit T. Diplomasi: tarihi teorisi kurumları ve uygulamaları / İstanbul: İstanbul Bilgi Üniversitesi yayınları, - 2014, 544 s.
5. Kodaman T. ve Ekrem Y. A. Kuruluşta yıkılışa kadar osmanlı diplomasi tarihi ve Türkiye'de bıraktığı miras // SDÜ fen edebiyat fakültesi sosyal bilimler dergisi, sayı. 22, 2010, - s. 75-92
6. Toklu V. Uluslararası ilişkiler / Ankara: İmaj yayınevi, - 2004, - 588 s.
7. Tuncer Hüner. Eski ve yeni diplomasi / Ankara: Ümit yayıncılık, - 1995, - 158 s.
8. Tuncer H. Küresel diplomasi /Ankara: Ümit yayıncılık, - 2006, - 208 s.

9. Uyar C. Dış politika oluşum sürecinde sivil toplum rolüne teorik bir bakış // Fenerbahçe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi, - 2021, cilt 1 (1), s. 82-96

10. Vranjes, Nevenko and Dejan, Zeljić, “Impact of globalization on diplomacy of small countries according to the ministry of foreign affairs” [Electronic resource] / URL: https://kipdf.com/impact-of-globalization-on-diplomacy-of-small-countries-according-to-the-ministr_5aaee5f41723dd415af865e5.html

11. Zharmukhanbetova N. Dış politika aracı olarak diplomasi ve Kazakistan Cumhuriyeti örneğinde kurumsal diplomasi / Yüksek lisans tezi, İzmir: Ege Üniversitesi, - 2010, - 130 s.

12. Neumann I.B. Globalisation and diplomacy [Electronic resource] / URL: <https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/45475/724%20Globalisation%20and%20Diplomacy.pdf>

13. Nicolson H. The evolution of diplomatic method / London: Greenwood Press, 1977. - 93 p.

14. Trunkos J. Changing diplomacy demands new type of diplomat [Electronic resource] / URL: https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=mlKt9ZMAAAAJ&citation_for_view=mlKt9ZMAAAAJ:9yKSN-GCB0IC

15. Hans-Georg W. Diplomacy and Globalization [Electronic resource] / URL: <http://www.hans-georg-wieck.com/data/Diplomacy%20and%20Globalization.pdf>